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Spectrophotometric Studies of the Chelates of Copper(II) with 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl Acetophenonesemicarbazone

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC studies on complex formation in iron(III)-2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone semicarbazone (5MeOAS) system have been reported earlier¹. The present communication describes the spectrophotometric study of green coloured complex formed by copper(II) and 5MeOAS.

Experimental and Results

5MeOAS was prepared as described earlier¹. Technical grade methanol was used after drying over anhydrous calcium chloride and then distilled. The stock solution of copper sulphate was prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of copper sulphate, the concentration of which was determined by standard gravimetric and volumetric methods.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Zeiss-specol using 1 cm matched cells. All measurements were carried out at $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ in a 50% methanol—50% water (by volume) medium.

The method of Vosburgh and Cooper² was employed to determine the nature of complexes. Mixtures containing 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 mole-ratios of iron(III) to 5MeOAS were prepared. Absorbance measurements were carried out between 400 nm and 750 nm. The observations showed the presence of only one complex with $\lambda_{max} = 640$ nm formed in the system.

The composition of the complex was determined by three different methods, Job's³ using equimolar solutions, slope-ratio⁴ and mole-ratio⁵ methods. It was found to be 1 : 1 in all the three cases.

Effect of variation of pH on the degree of complex formation was studied. The optimum pH-range was observed to be 3.8 to 6.5 in which the complex was stable for several days.

The apparent stability constant, $\log K = 4.7 \pm 0.1$ of the complex was calculated from the absorbance data by the method of Mukherji and Dey.⁶

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Synthesis of 5,7,8-Trimethoxy-3-methylchromone derivatives

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BENZO- γ -PYRONES or chromones having hydroxy or methoxy substituents in 5,7,8-positions are of interest as they are found in a great variety of compounds. Wiley¹ synthesised several chromones, which are found to have bronchodilator activity. We report here the synthesis of polymethoxy chromone derivatives, as this type of compounds, not only occur in nature but possess valuable therapeutic properties.

1,2,3,5-Tetramethoxy benzene², on Friedel-Crafts propionylation with propionic anhydride and anhydrous aluminium chloride afforded 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxy propiophenone³ (I), which when subjected to Kostanecki-Robinson acylation with acetic anhydride and freshly fused sodium acetate, yielded a product, which was insoluble in alkali. The I.R. spectrum of the product showed a strong band in the carbonyl region viz., 1660 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl C = O group). It has been assigned 5,7,8-trimethoxy-2,3-dimethylchromone⁴ structure (IIa).

I

II

a : R = $-\text{CH}_3$

b : R = $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation of compound(I), with benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate afforded 5,7,8-trimethoxy-3-methylflavone(IIb). The I.R. Spectrum of (IIb) showed a strong band in the carbonyl region viz., 1600 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl C = O group) and did not develop any colouration with alcoholic ferric-chloride solution.

Experimental

5,7,8-Trimethoxy-2,3-dimethylchromone (IIa) :

A mixture of 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxy-propio-phenone² (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 ml) and freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) was heated at 180° in an oil bath for 10 hr. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove unreacted compound. It was then washed with water and dried. The product was dissolved in benzene and the solution was run through a short column of alumina. The compound was eluted with benzene. Evaporation of the solvent left the residue, which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 162°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 63.52; H, 6.01. C₁₄H₁₆O₅ requires : C, 63.63; H, 6.11%).

5,7,8-Trimethoxy-3-methylflavone (IIb) :

A mixture of 3,4,6-Trimethoxy propiophenone (1 g.), benzoic anhydride (4 g.) and freshly fused sodium benzoate (5 g.) was heated at 200° in an oil bath for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was boiled with water and filtered. The product was treated with aq. sodium hydroxide solution (30 ml, 5%) for about 30 min. The insoluble compound was filtered, washed with water and dried. The compound, in methanol, was passed through a short column of alumina and eluted with methanol. Evaporation of the solvent gave the residue, which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 164°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found : C, 69.55; H, 5.52. C₁₉H₁₈O₅ requires : C, 69.93; H, 5.71%).

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Thin Layer Chromatographic Studies of Some Substituted Thioureas

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PAPER chromatographic studies of some substituted thioureas have been reported¹⁻⁴ but thin layer chromatographic (TLC) studies seem to have received little attention. The present work was carried out on TLC of some substituted thioureas.

Experimental

The thioureas were prepared by the usual methods⁵, purified by crystallization from suitable solvents. Nitrogen and sulphur contents in the compounds were estimated by Kjeldahl and Messenger's method respectively, and were well in agreement with the theoretical values. The melting points also agreed with the reported values.

Silica gel G was used as an adsorbent and small glass plates were used as carriers. Silica gel slurry was prepared in methanol and the plates were coated with the adsorbent by immersion technique. The plates were allowed to dry and the layers were activated by keeping the plates in an oven at 150° for 2-3 hr. The dried plates were marked with a pin for the spot line.

The substances were dissolved in ethanol. These solutions were then spotted on the plates with a 10 λ pipette. The spot had a diameter between 2 to 5 mm. After the spot had dried, the plates were kept in an inclined position in a chamber containing the solvent. The chamber was closed with a glass cover to saturate the chamber atmosphere with solvent vapour.

When the solvent had travelled sufficiently along the plates, they were taken out and the solvent front was marked. The time taken by the solvent to travel along the plate was 30 to 40 min. The temperature of the chamber was kept constant during the experiment. The spots on the plates were visualized by two different methods : (i) by exposing the dried plates to iodine vapour whence thioureas appear as dark brown spots; (ii) by using Grote's reagent⁶; the dried plates are sprayed with this reagent and heated in an oven for 30 min, thereupon the thioureas appeared as deep blue spots. The R_f values were then calculated and are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1. R_f VALUES OF THIOUREAS IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS

Compounds	A	B	C	D	E	F
phenyl thiourea	0.63	0.98	0.26	0.72	0.69	—
diphenyl thiourea	0.97	0.91	0.40	0.77	0.76	—
dibenzyl thiourea	0.93	0.82	0.35	0.79	0.97	—
<i>o</i> -tolyl thiourea	0.37	0.96	0.41	0.97	0.97	0.70
<i>m</i> -tolyl thiourea	0.39	0.94	0.37	0.98	0.93	0.84
<i>p</i> -tolyl thiourea	0.59	0.96	0.35	0.81	0.94	0.83
<i>o</i> -methoxy phenyl thiourea	0.59	—	0.26	0.74	0.94	0.93
<i>p</i> -methoxy phenyl thiourea	0.66	—	0.78	0.81	0.90	0.94

A—water saturated chloroform

B—benzene : ethanol (1 : 1, V : V)

C—chloroform : carbon tetrachloride (1 : 1, V : V)

D—ethanol

E—dioxane

F—ethyl acetate : carbon tetrachloride (1 : 1, V : V).